

UOT: 541.128.13:524.941. 547.211:542.943

OXIDATIVE CONVERSION OF METHANE. EFFECT OF CATALYST AND PERSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS OF REACTION

¹ E.H. Ismailov, ¹ D.B.Taghiyev, ¹ S.M. Zulfugarova, ¹ G.R. Azimova, ¹ S.N. Osmanova, ² J.W. Thybaut

¹Institute of Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry named after acad. M.Naghiyev ANAS,

² Ghent University, B-9052 Gent, Belgium

etibar.ismailov@gmail.com

The well-known MnNaW catalysts based on SiO₂ for oxidative condensation of methane (OCM) were synthesized by various methods, characterized by X-ray diffractometry (XRD), scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive elemental analysis (SEM/EDX), electron magnetic resonance (EMR) spectroscopy, N₂ adsorption-desorption measurements, and tested as OCM catalysts at atmospheric pressure to convert into a mixture of ethylene + carbon oxides for further hydroformylation to propylene. The structural and catalytic features of the synthesized systems are discussed. The necessity of using mainly X-ray diffraction, Raman, and EMR methods for studying catalysts in situ mode in combination with online MS analysis of gas-phase reaction products to establish the nature of catalytically active phases, centers, their mechanism of functioning, activation of CH₄ with the formation of C-C bond for the synthesis of hydrocarbons C₂ and C₂₊ is considered.

Keywords: oxidative conversion of methane, NaMnW/SiO₂ catalyst, ethylene-carbon monoxide mixture, magnetic, texture properties

INTRODUCTION

Oxidative condensation of methane (OCM) is one of the promising methods for processing natural gas into an ethane-ethylene mixture. A limiting factor in the practical implementation of the process is the low yield of target products. The best catalysts make it possible to obtain selectivity for C₂-products up to 70-80% at a methane conversion of 25-30 % [1, 2]. A tempting approach based on a combination of the OCM reaction to produce ethylene and carbon monoxide in the reaction products with the required CO/C₂H₄ ratio with the hydroformylation reaction of this mixture to propylene is used in project C123 of the EU Horizon2020 program. This work presents the results of testing nanostructured oxide systems MnNaW/SiO₂ as catalysts for the OCM reaction to obtain gas-phase mixtures with an equimolar ratio C₂H₄/CO, and discusses the structural and catalytic features of the synthesized systems.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Catalysts preparation

To prepare the catalysts, mesoporous silica matrices preliminarily were synthesized, using tetraethoxysilane, TEOS, cetyl-tri-methyl-ammonium bromide, CTAB (samples 1), TEOS, triethanolamine, TEA (samples 2) TEOS, citric acid, CA (samples 3) as precursors. Further, the reaction mixture containing an aqueous solution of surfactant, TEOS and ammonia was kept in a thermostat for several hours at room temperature until mesoporous silica was formed. Then the solution was filtered, the resulting precipitate was washed with distilled water and dried in air at room

temperature. Salts of the corresponding metals were introduced into the hydrophobic part of the "template/silicon dioxide" composite by impregnating them with aqueous solutions of samples of 1,2,3 mesoporous silicon dioxide. The resulting gel after drying at room temperature is placed in a drying oven and kept at 80-100 °C for 3-4 hours until completely dry. The final heat treatment of the obtained sample is carried out in a muffle furnace at 850 °C for 4 hours.

Catalysts characterization

The catalysts were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Hitachi S-3400N) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (EDX; Oxford), X-ray diffractometers XRD D2, Bruker, Germany and XRD TD3500, China; Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, iC3000, Thermo Scientific, USA; EPR spectrometer EMX_micro, Bruker, Germany; the specific surface area and total pore volume of the samples was determined by low-temperature adsorption of nitrogen using SORBI-MS (Russia) and Belsorp Mini II, BEL Japan Inc. instruments. The powders were activated for 18 hours under vacuum at 90°C to remove moisture before measuring the texture values. Radical freezing system in combination with JES-PE-3X, Jeol EPR spectrometer and home made quartz flow reactor connected with radicals freezing system for registration of hydro- carbon and peroxide radicals and investigation of their concentration as a function of reaction condition and type of catalyst. The reactions were carried out at temperatures 550 -850°C. The synthesized samples as catalysts for the OCM reaction were tested using a flow-through setup with a fixed catalyst bed. Gas-phase products of the reaction after the reactor were analyzed using Agilent 7280A (USA) and LXM 80 (Russia) chromatographs. Helium was used as the carrier gas. The OCM reaction was carried out at 700 - 900°C and atmospheric pressure. The catalyst weighed amount was 0.2 g of the 0.25 - 0.5 mm fraction, the volumetric flow rate of the mixture was up to 140 ml/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Below are the results of a study of the elemental, phase composition, magnetic properties, morphology, and structural-porous characteristics of the synthesized Na-W-Mn-containing catalysts based on SiO₂ obtained by various preparation methods.

Elemental and phase composition, surface structure and distribution of active elements in catalysts.

Electron micrographs show that the duration of the calcination of the samples significantly affects the morphology and structure of the surface. Regarding the effect of the duration of calcination of the samples on the distribution of active components in the catalyst structure, an EDX analyzer of an electron microscope is used and the surfaces of these samples were scanned at 5 randomly selected points of the surface. Comparison of these EDX spectra indicates a noticeable effect of the duration of calcination of the samples at 850°C on the distribution of catalytically active components in the catalyst structure.

X-ray diffraction patterns of samples show the presence of two different phases of the SiO₂ matrix - cristabolite and tridymite and changes in the phase composition of the matrix with an increase in the calcination temperature of the samples from 850 to 1000 °C with the introduction of these active components into SiO₂. X-ray diffraction patterns of samples calcined for 4 hours: a) SiO₂ at 850°C; b) SiO₂ at 1000°C; c) MnNaW/SiO₂ at 1000°C are given in fig.1.

EMR data

For all samples two types of EPR spectra are observed. The first one with $g = 2.000$ and an hyperfine constant of ~ 90 G is characteristic for isolated Mn^{2+} ions, and the second with $g = 2.01-2.1$ and $\Delta H = 600-1100$ G belongs to $MnOx$, most likely to Mn_2O_3 nanoparticles [3]. Mn^{3+} is not a Kramers ion ($3 d^4$, $S = 2$), and it does not show EPR signals at the X-band frequency [4]. Figure 2 shows the EPR spectra of sample 1 at 300 K.

Fig.1. X-ray diffraction patterns of samples calcined for 4 hours: a) SiO_2 at 850 °C; b) SiO_2 at 1000 °C; c) $2Mn-0.8Na-3.2W/SiO_2$ at 1000 °C

Fig.2. EPR spectra at 300K of $2Mn-0.8Na-3.2W/SiO_2$ sample 1 calcined at 850 °C for 4 hours: a,b) before and c) after 10 hours OCM reaction at 798 °C; $(CH_4/O_2)=4$.

It was shown that the observed $MnOx$ nanoparticles are superparamagnetic and weakly ferromagnetic above and below the blocking temperature, accordingly. The dependent of the composition and size of $MnOx$ nanoparticles on the reaction conditions is observed. The evaluated size of the observed $MnOx$ nanoparticles is less than 10 nm [5].

Texture properties

In table 1 the values of specific surface area and the volume of pore of these samples before and after 15 hours working in OCM reaction are given. As can be seen from these data effect of the reaction condition on the texture parameters of the samples is significant.

Table 1

The values of specific surface area and the volume of pore of these samples before and after 15 hours working in OCM reaction

Samples*	BET (m^2/g)		Total pore volume, $p/p_0 = 0.99$ ($cm^3 g^{-1}$)	
	a*	b*	A	B
1	116.8	46.1	0.590	0.232
2	36.0	4,4	0.206	0.025
3	38.2	8,3	0.373	0.081

* a, b - accordingly before and after 15 hours testing of the samples in reaction OCM.

Catalysts Testing

The synthesized catalysts exhibit different catalytic activity, depending on their preparation method. Methane conversion of up to 47.7 % and a selectivity of C2 and C3 hydrocarbons in the amount of up to 86.7 % and a yield of up to 27.4 % were observed. The selectivity ratio (C2+C3)/(CO+CO₂) is approximately 1 with a fairly high yield (25.2 %) (C2+C3) for sample 1 and slightly more than 1 for sample 2 (for yield) 24.3 %). The ratio of C₂H₄ / (CO+CO₂) is approximately 1 for both samples with the same yield of C2+C3 hydrocarbons. An increase in temperature from 778 to 874 °C leads to an increase in ethylene selectivity and the yield of C2+C3 hydrocarbons. Stability of catalyst as a function of OCM reaction duration is shown in fig.3.

Fig.3. Dependence of methane conversion (■), selectivity of C2+ hydrocarbons (▲) and the yield of C2+ hydrocarbons (◆) on the duration time of the OCM reaction at the ratio CH₄/O₂ = 4, (reaction temperature 812 °C, catalyst weight 0.2 g, gas mixture flow rate 120 ml / min.)

Conversion of methane and oxygen without (◆, □, respectively) and in the presence (▲, ▲) of the catalyst in the OCM reaction as a function of the reaction temperature at the ratio CH₄/O₂= 4, (catalyst weight 0.2 g, gas mixture flow rate 120 ml/min.) is demonstrated in fig.4.

Fig.4. Conversion of methane and oxygen without (◆, □, respectively) and in the presence (▲, ▲) of the catalyst in the OCM reaction as a function of the reaction temperature at the ratio CH₄/O₂= 4, (catalyst weight 0.2 g, gas mixture flow rate 120 ml/min.)

Conversion and selectivity as a function of CH₄/O₂ ratio are The full stoichiometric equation of the OCM reaction according to the output data can be written in the form:

for the case (CH₄/O₂)=2 we have

and for the case (CH₄/O₂)=4 we have

According to experimental data the ratio $(\text{CH}_4/\text{O}_2) \geq 4$ more acceptable for OCM reaction.

Fig.5. Dependence of the conversion of methane (▲) selectivities of C₂+ hydrocarbons (o), CO (▲) and CO₂ (◆), the yield of C₂+ hydrocarbons (□), C₂H₄/C₂H₆ ratio (●) in the presence of a catalyst in the OCM reaction on the CH₄/O₂ ratio, (catalyst weight 0.2 g, gas mixture flow rate 120 ml / min.)

Conversion and selectivity as a function of flow rate of gas mixture are given in fig.6.

Fig.6. Dependence of the conversion of methane (▲) selectivities of C₂+ hydrocarbons (o), CO (◆) and CO₂ (■), the yield of C₂+ hydrocarbons (■) on the flow rate of gas mixture in OCM reaction at a ratio $(\text{CH}_4/\text{O}_2) = 4$, (catalyst weight 0.2 g, reaction temperature 798°C)

If we assume that nanosized Mn₂O₃ particles are active centers of the OCM reaction:

then it can also be assumed that methane is activated by oxygen of Mn₂O₃ with the separation of the hydrogen atom and the formation of the methyl radical CH₃[•] [6,7]. Further, under the reaction conditions, these radicals combine and turn into ethane, and when interacting with oxygen, into CH₃O₂[•] radicals, which are further oxidized to CO and CO₂. In the case of an excess of oxygen under the reaction conditions, ethylene is also easily oxidized to carbon oxides.

Radical freezing system in combination with JES-PE-3X, Jeol EPR spectrometer and home made quartz flow reactor connected with radicals freezing Dewar for registration of hydrocarbon and peroxide radicals and investigation of their concentration as a function of reaction condition and type of catalyst is given in fig. 7.

Only RO_2^\bullet radicals were detected and their concentration is increased as the ratio CH_4/O_2 is increase. CH_3^\bullet radical is not detected because the liquid nitrogen temperature is high enough to detect the CH_3^\bullet radical and therefore only RO_2^\bullet radicals are detected. The reactions were carried out at temperatures of 550 - 850 °C.

Fig.7. Radical freezing system in combination with JES-PE-3XQ, Jeol EPR spectrometer and home made quartz flow reactor connected with Dewar for registration of hydrocarbon and peroxide radicals. Here: a) 1- Catalyst; 2- Capillary with the end beginning from the surface (no more than 0,5 mm); 3- Heater; 4.-Dewar vessel; 5 –Reaction products outlet; b) Dewar vessel with capillary

X-ray diffractometry data show the effect of active elements introduced into the SiO_2 matrix on the phase composition of the matrix. With increasing the calcination temperature from 850 to 1000°C, no noticeable changes are observed in the diffractograms of the matrix. However, the diffraction patterns of the 2Mn-0.8Na-3.2W/ SiO_2 samples, along with the formation of the MnO_x and Na_2WO_4 phases of active elements, show the presence of two phases of the SiO_2 matrix differing in structure - cristabolite and tridymite; with an increase in the calcination temperature of samples containing Mn, Na, W, from 850 to 1000°C, the phase composition of the matrix changes. The used $MnNaW/SiO_2$ catalyst is multicomponent and, as shown by the X-ray diffractometry data, consists of the phases MnO_x , Na_2WO_4 , and SiO_2 . At the reaction temperature OCM, i.e. 750-850°C, one of these phases - Na_2WO_4 is in a melted state (the values of the melting and decomposition temperature of Na_2WO_4 are equal to 696 and 1200°C, respectively). The phases MnO_x (MnO , Mn_2O_3 , MnO_2) and SiO_2 have a melting point above 850°C, i.e. under the reaction conditions Na_2WO_4 , covering the surface of crystalline SiO_2 (with cristobalite and/or tridymite structure) in the form of a film, and nanosized MnO_x particles contained in it, as shown by EMR data. This example underline the peculiarities of high-temperature reactions catalyzed

by multicomponent systems, the components of which are in different states of aggregation under the reaction conditions.

CONCLUSION

The synthesis of a stable OCM catalyst with a conversion of more than 35% and a selectivity for C₂ hydrocarbons up to 80% is considered practically acceptable. But:

1. If we use the MnNaW/SiO₂ and its modification forms as catalysts for OCM reaction we have to work at the temperature 750-850°C with the ratio CH₄/O₂ >4 with flow rates of the gas mixture (CH₄+O₂) more than 100 ml/min. In this case we have the quietly high yield of target products, but not enough for practical purposes. The experimental results show that after 15 hours of working in OCM reaction the activity, selectivity and yield of catalysts decrease approximately for 10-15%. We have to take into account the instability of phase composition of these catalysts under reaction conditions also.
2. To use catalysts of new compositions that allow the OCM reaction to be carried out at temperatures below the ignition of ethane and ethylene (~ 600°C). In this case, we will need to carry out studies using in-situ EPR and Raman spectroscopy in combination with mass spectroscopy of surface and gas-phase products of the OCM reaction. These studies make it possible to find ways to stabilize methyl radicals with their subsequent recombination on the surface with the formation of ethane, to separate and control the stages of recombination of methyl radicals on the surface and in the gas phase, and thereby allow controlling the OCM process. For catalysts with the composition MnNaW/SiO₂, prepared using TEOS and CTAB as precursors, methane conversion up to 47.7 % was observed, selectivity for hydrocarbons C₂, C₃ in total up to 86.7 % and yield up to 27 mas.%; the selectivity ratio (C₂ +C₃)/CO was ~1 at a rather high yield (25.2 %) of C₂, C₃ hydrocarbons. An increase in temperature from 778 to 874°C led to an increase in selectivity for C₂,C₃ hydrocarbons. For these catalysts, the specific surface area was 100-120 m²/g and after 10 hours of operation at a temperature of 800-850° C decreased significantly, but they average pore diameter is in the range of 2-50 nm still, so the behavior of these catalysts will be typical for mesoporous materials. Comparison of EDX spectra indicates a noticeable effect of the temperature and duration of calcination of the samples on the distribution of catalytically active components in the catalyst structure. We consider it expedient to carry out, first of all, in situ X-ray diffraction, Raman, and EMR studies in combination with mass spectroscopic analysis of gas-phase products of the reaction to detailize, refine the "structure-activity" models of the OCM reaction with participation of MnNaW/SiO₂ catalysts [8].

Acknowledgements: This work is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No.814557. The authors are grateful to Richard Heyn (SINTEF, Oslo, Norway) for help in measuring the texture characteristics of the samples.

REFERENCES

1. Kondratenko E.V., Peppel T., Seeburg D., Kondratenko V.A., Kalevaru N., Martin A., Wohlrab S. "Methane conversion into different hydrocarbons or oxygenates:

- current status and future perspectives in catalyst development and reactor operation”, Catal. Sci. Technol.2017, 7(2), pp.366–381
2. C. Karakaya, R.J. Kee. “Progress in the direct catalytic conversion of methane to fuels and chemicals”, Progr. Energy Combust. Sci.2016, 55, pp. 60–97
 3. S.Mukherjee, A.K. Pal, S. Bhattacharya, J. Raittila. “Magnetism of Mn₂O₃ nanocrystals dispersed in a silica matrix.: Size effects and phase transformations”, Phys.RevB.74, 104413 p
 4. D.P. Goldberg, J. Telser, J. Krzystek et al., “EPR spectra from “EPR-Silent” species: high-field EPR spectroscopy of manganese(III) porphyrins,” J. of the Amer.Chem. Society.1997,119 (37), pp.8722–8723
 5. Walter S. D. Folly and Ronaldo S. de Biasi “Determination of Particle Size Distribution by FMR Measurements”, Braz. J. Phys.2001, 31 (3), pp.398–401
 6. A.I. Suleimanov, E.G. Ismailov, S.M. Aliev, V.D. Sokolovskii, “Contribution of one-electron acceptor centers to oxidative dimerization of methane”,React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.1987, pp.34, 51–55
 7. Wang J., Rosyynek M.P., Lunsford J.H. “Oxidative Coupling of Methane over Oxide-Supported Sodium-Manganese Catalysts”, J. Catal.1995,115 (2), pp. 390–402
 8. Daniel Kiani, Sagar Sourav, Jonas Baltrusaitis, Israel E.Wachs, “Oxidative Coupling of Methane (OCM) by SiO₂ – supported Tungsten Oxide Catalysts Promoted with Mn and Na”, ACS Catal.2019 9, (7), pp.5912–5928

ОКИСЛИТЕЛЬНАЯ КОНВЕРСИЯ МЕТАНА. ЭФФЕКТ КАТАЛИЗАТОРА И ПЕРСПЕКТИВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РЕАКЦИИ

¹Э.Г.Исмаилов, ¹Д.Б. Тагиев, ¹С.М. Зульфугарова, ¹Г.Р.Азимова, ¹С.Н.Османова,
²Й.У. Тибот

¹Институт Катализа и Неорганической Химии им.акад.М.Ф. Нагиева НАНА,
²Университет Гент, В-9052 Гент, Бельгия
etibar.ismailov@gmail.com

Хорошо известные катализаторы MnNaW на основе SiO₂ для окислительной конденсации метана (ОКМ) были синтезированы различными методами, охарактеризованы методами рентгеновской дифрактометрии (XRD), сканирующей электронной микроскопии с энергодисперсионным элементным анализом (SEM/EDX), электронного магнитного резонанса. (ЭМР), текстурные характеристики по адсорбции-десорбции N₂ и испытаны в качестве катализаторов реакции ОКМ в углеводороды C₂ и C₂₊, в смесь этилен + оксиды углерода при атмосферном давлении с целью гидроформилирования последнего в пропилен. Обсуждены структурные и каталитические особенности синтезированных систем. Указаны каталитически активные центры, механизм реакции ОКМ с их участием с образованием связи С-С и углеводородов на этой основе.

Ключевые слова: окислительная конверсия метана, катализатор MnNaW/SiO₂, фазовый состав, магнитные, текстурные свойства, углеводороды C₂, C₂₊, смесь этилен+оксиды углерода.

METANIN OKSIDLƏŞDİRİCİ KONDENSASIYASI. KATALİZATORUN TƏSİRİ VƏ REAKSIYANIN PERSPEKTİV İSTİQAMƏTLƏRİ

¹ E.H. İsmayılov, ¹ D.B. Tağıyev, ¹ S.M. Zülfügarova, ¹ G.R. Əzimova,
¹ S.N. Osmanova, ² Joris Thybaut
¹ Akad. M. Nağıyev adına Kataliz və Qeyri-üzvi Kimya İnstitutu, AMEA,
² Ghent Universiteti, B-9052 Ghent, Belçika
etibar.ismailov@gmail.com

Metanın oksidləşdirici kondensasiyası (MOK) üçün SiO₂ əsaslı məlum MnNaW katalizatorları müxtəlif üsullarla sintez edilmiş, onların rentgen difraktometriyası (XRD), elektron skan mikroskopu enerji dispersion element analizi ilə birgə (SEM/EDX), elektron maqnit rezonansı (EMR) spektroskopiyası, N₂ adsorbsiya-desorbsiyası əsasında textur xarakteristikaları müəyyən edilmiş, atmosfer təzyiqində metanın C₂, C₂₊ karbohidrogenlərə, etilen+karbon oksidləri qarışıqına və sonuncunun propilenə hidroformilləşdirilməsi reaksiyalarında katalizator kimi sınağı keçirilmişdir. Sintez edilmiş sistemlərin struktur və katalitik xüsusiyyətləri müzakirə olunmuş, katalitik aktiv mərkəzlər göstərilmiş, onların iştirakı ilə C-C rabitəsinin və karbohidrogenlərin əmələ gəlməsinə gətirib çıxaran mexanizm verilmişdir. **Açar sözlər:** metanın oksidləşdirici kondensasiyası, katalizator MnNaW/SiO₂, faza tərkibi, maqnit, textur xassələri, C₂, C₂₊ karbohidrogenləri, etilen+karbon oksidləri qarışıqı.